

My tips to be successful in the EIC accelerator pilot

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[EIC accelerator pilot](#) has become one of the most important (and frustrating) call for SMEs.

I am working in the call since 2015 and participants always ask about how to fund a proposal. Unfortunately, there is not a magical recipe but there are five tips that I hope will help you to enhance your success probabilities since the beginning:

1. (MARKET) Your unique added value proposition is aligned with H2020 priorities and it is focused on a real market opportunity for your company.
2. (TECHNOLOGY) The excellence section clearly explains why you are a technology-based company with proprietary IPR items that demonstrate the starting technology maturity.
3. (PENDING STEPS) The implementation plan is realistic with clear actions, milestones and KPIs that limit the risks and forecast the return on investment for future investors.
4. (BEST VALUE FOR MONEY) Your business plan includes a detailed investment plan specifying not only the project/company needs but also the previous rounds figures, company KPIs achieved and the entrance/exit strategies for the new investors you are looking for.
5. (COMPANY) Your team is excellent considering not only the technical issues that can arise but also the necessary managerial roles to deploy the business plan at EU level with a high growing rate.